

RadAR Signature Validation by Comparison to Measured Data

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1 Abstract

Software implementation of asymptotic prediction methods requires validation against target geometries exhibiting both specular and non-specular scattering mechanisms. Validation of radar signature predictions using measured signature data requires accurate test target dimensions and detailed measurement facility setup. Use of precise Computer Aided Design (CAD) target models are essential.

This paper¹ compares monostatic RADAR signature measurement data to CADDSCAT² synthetic predictions for a 'standard' set of primitive and complex targets. Prediction accuracy is compared for temporal, spatial and spectral signature accuracy. The limitations of the CADDSCAT asymptotic predictions is accessed.

2 Introduction

Validation of asymptotic prediction methods is required to access the frequency and geometry range over which accurate predictions are obtained. This paper presents the validation of a radar signature prediction code called CADDSCAT. CADDSCAT implements the Physical Optics and Incremental Length Diffraction Coefficient (ILDC) asymptotic methods for prediction of surface specular fields and edge diffracted fields. Multibounce field contributions are incorporated via the Shooting and Bouncing Rays (SBR) Method. All three theories require electrically large, smooth targets. Appropriate test target data and CAD models were amassed into a database. The validation is completed using the radar signature measurements.

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²CADDSCAT is a high frequency Physical Optics (PO), Physical Theory of Diffraction (PTD) based radar signature prediction code developed by McDonald Douglas Corporation.

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3 Test Targets and Measurements

Choice of test targets used in this validation was based on several factors. Initially 25 appropriate test objects were considered for this validation. Targets were chosen so as to have five wavelengths along their surfaces when possible. [1, 113] The next criteria was to ensure that the target set as a whole exhibited scattering due to specular reflection, edge diffraction and multibounce scattering. In addition objects with doubly curved surfaces were required to test CAD geometry modeling accuracy. A missile model was chosen as the complex test target exhibiting scattering centers from curved surfaces, edges, cavities, and surface shadowing features. Accurate accounting of shadowing between surfaces of a complex geometry is needed to obtaining a correct radar signature prediction. Both Perfect Electrical Conductor (PEC) and dielectric test targets were used for validation.

Figure 1: Unsymmetric Ogive Predictions, Elevation = 0°, L = 7.5 inches r = 1 inch, **SOLID** curve is measured data, **DASHED** curves is synthetic data

This research used measured data from the Naval Air Warfare Center at China Lakes³. [2] The China Lake data provided low radar signature target measurements of conespheres, ogives, and an almond target. Measurements were completed for the missile target at The Ohio State University anechoic chamber.

³Data measurements for the Electromagnetic Code Consortium(EMCC) were completed by personnel from the Ames Research Center and The China Lake Naval Weapons Center.

4 Results

A candidate validation target set of measurements and CAD geometry files now exists for future validations. CADDSCAT's use of bicubic spline geometric models allows for accurate predictions of doubly-curved targets. Figure 3 is a PO prediction for an unsymmetric ogive target. No calibration data was available for the ogive measurements. The data was shift down by 10 dBsm to account for the 14 inch calibration sphere data that was not available. Lack of proper target configuration data creates an uncertainty for this measured data. Prediction of a dielectric coated ogive at 18 gigahertz(GHz) was completed using constitutive parameter at frequencies of 4 and 10 GHz. Nonavailability of constitutive parameters over the frequency band contributes to further uncertainty in modeling the coated ogive target.

Figure 4 is the measured radar signature for a missile target. The PO prediction of Figure 4 no longer provides an adequate prediction for this complex target. Vast improvements were obtained once edge diffraction and multibounce calculations were added to the PO prediction of Figure 4.

Time domain impulse response predictions were obtained by an inverse fourier transform of the frequency domain prediction data. Impulse response analysis is used to validate a prediction's accuracy through comparison of scattering center location and amplitudes. Illumination of the missile's nose accurately predicts the two major scattering center locations at the trailing edges of the fins (see Figure 4). Alignment uncertainties of $\pm 0.5^\circ$ in elevation and $\pm 1^\circ$ in azimuth and elevation constitute a significant error source when comparing time domain predictions.

5 Conclusions

CADDSCAT's implementation of the PO, ILDC and the SBR prediction methods provides excellent first-order radar signature predictions for complex, electrically large targets. The target measurements used have highlighted the limitation of PO only predictions. The extension of the PO predictions for specular predictions of dielectric coated targets was validated. The validation geometries used are a candidate set for use in future code validation efforts.

References

- [1] Knott, Eugene F., et al. *Radar Cross Section*. Artech House, 1985.
- [2] Wang, Helen T. G., et al. *Radar Cross Section Measurement Data On Low-Cross-Section Targets: Part 1 and 2*. Informal Report TM-7002, Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, CA 93555-6001: Radio Frequency Guidance Division Intercept Weapons Department, October 1991

Figure 2: Frequency and Time Domain Data versus Predictions, Length = 30.28 inches, **SOLID** curves are measured data, **DASHED** curves are synthetic data